

THE ROLE OF MUSIC THEORETICAL KNOWLEDGE IN IMPROVING MUSIC LITERACY IN STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7417684>

Abstract: In this article, opinions are based on the importance of musical knowledge in music theory classes in the formation of musical literacy in students, and the role of musical literacy in a musician.

Key words: Music theory, Harmony science, musical signs, diapason, note, musical sound, temperament.

In the process of music lessons, the main form of organizing educational activities for improving students' musical literacy is a group lesson. At present, it is of great importance to form musical literacy among students studying in music and art schools. Because it is impossible to understand the true essence of music without the knowledge of music literacy. Students should first have an understanding of notes, whole note length, count, half note length, quarter note length, eighth or sixteenth notes, etc. He should be able to explain well the placement of notes, pauses, octaves.

There are 3 characteristics of musical sound: it is necessary to understand about *their height, hardness, and timbre*. The position of the notes on the 5 main lines and the position on the additional lines from below and above, and the concepts of octaves, the names of the strings on the instrument, the location of the notes, the tuning, the student should be clear about which octave is played on how many strings of the instrument and must explain fluently. To a student who has just started to learn to play an instrument together with music literacy and *solfeggio* lessons, the student's knowledge will be further increased.

The successful mastery of musical performance of a musically literate student largely depends on his ability and literacy. During the performance, the student should hold the body in such a way that it is convenient for all the actions of the performer. In addition, it is necessary to achieve a beautiful appearance of the body and instrument grip. The performance styles of each musical instrument are different and are performed through its own methods.

Musical literacy plays a key role in the musician's performance, and musical elements such as note length, measures, pitch, rhythm, meter, pauses, dynamic signs, melismas are important in improving performance skills and effective performance. Including, the position during performance should be comfortable from all sides, and the body position should be kept free. The task of forming the

habit of performing for a long time without getting tired in the student does not appear by itself. This skill can be developed through regular training. Musical sound characteristics. One of the types of art that penetrates into the general public is the art of music. In it, the artistic content is expressed through sounds (*melody*) and is based on certain rules that connect the specific means of expression of music.

These rules and traditions were created as a result of the centuries-old experience of folk (folklore) and classical music. In order to play or sing any kind of music, it is important to know music literacy. Therefore, the teaching of this subject initially covers the performance of musical works and the acquisition of knowledge about the relationships of sounds and intervals that exist in them.

Music of any form and content consists of various components, and music literacy is divided into several branches, such as elementary theory of music, harmony, analysis of musical works, polyphony, and instrumental studies.

Within the framework of this research, among other things, the characteristics of musical sound, the technology of its expression in sheet music, the main expressive means of music: meter-rhythm, scale, harmony; the ratio of two sounds (interval), the ratio of three or more sounds (*chord*) and the musical content expressed through them; and, the possibilities of tonalities to express musical content are analyzed analytically.

An artistic image is reflected in musical works in a unique way, that is, as a synthesis of certain sounds and tones. In musical works, form and content are important as elements that complement each other.

In the course of the elementary theory of music, the word sound means two different concepts: the first is sound in a physical state; the second is sound in the sense state. For example, as a result of the vibration of a flexible object, the string of a musical instrument, longitudinal wave vibrations are formed in the air. These vibrations create a sound wave. They spread from the sound source in different directions. The general chain of this event takes place as follows: source of sound waves - sound waves - impact of sound waves on the hearing organ - transmission of the stimuli received through hearing analyzers to the brain.

From a physical point of view, hertz¹ (*hts*) is the number of oscillations of an oscillating body per second as a measure of oscillations accepted. When sound waves are received by the hearing organ, they affect it and pass through the nerve structure (analyzer) to the brain, causing a sensation of sound.

¹ Hertz is a term named after the physicist who discovered this phenomenon.

It is known that we hear a lot of different sounds in our daily life. But not all these sounds are used in music. Our hearing organs have the ability to distinguish between musical sounds and noisy sounds. Noisy sounds, such as crackling, humming, screeching, hissing, thumping, etc., do not have a specific pitch, so these sounds are not used in music².

Theoretically, musical sound has four different physical properties. They consist of pitch, length, loudness, and timbre. The height of the resounding sound depends on the vibration speed, that is, the frequency of the oscillating flexible body. The faster the vibration, the louder the sound, and the slower the vibration, the lower the sound. The duration of the resounding sound depends on the wave amplitude of the vibrating body. The length or shortness of a sound does not change its physical character, but from the point of view of music, the length of the sound is another characteristic of it and is of great importance. The duration of the sound depends on the continuation of the vibration of the sound source. For example, the wider the vibration of the sound source when the sound starts, the longer the sound decays. In this case, the body that is the source of sound must vibrate freely.

A series of sounds with a certain pitch relationship is called a musical structure. The arrangement of the sounds of the structure according to its height is called the sound line, and the sound is called its step. The full range of sounds of the musical structure includes 88 different sounds. These sounds (i.e. from the lowest pitch to the highest pitch) range from 16 Hz to 4176 Hz. These are the sounds that the human ear can comfortably hear.

Since the human vocal range is approximately 60 to 1000 Hz, most musical instruments produce sound within this range. Sounds are called with syllabic and letter names. Seven independent names are given to the main steps of the musical structure:

With a joint	Do	Re	Mi	Fa	Sol	Lya	Si
With letters	C	D	E	F	G	A	H

² Modern orchestras also use percussion instruments that do not have a specific pitch. For example, a triangle, a small drum, copper trays (plates), a large drum, etc. Composers use them as additional instruments to make a musical statement more expressive.

These names given to the main stages were formed in the Middle Ages. These major steps correspond to the sounds of the white keys of the piano and consist of 52 *major* keys. Due to its simplicity and brevity, the literal structure is widely used in our Republic and many foreign countries to represent tonalities, and to represent sounds, it is used only in scientific and musical literature. In some European countries, such as Germany, Great Britain and the Netherlands, the letter structure is still the main one today.

The name of the seven main steps in the musical scale is repeated at a certain time and thus includes all the sounds of the main steps. This is the result of every eighth note on the white keys, numbered upwards, vibrating twice as fast as the first note. Therefore, it corresponds to the second higher tone of the first initial sound and sounds in harmony with it.

The range of sounds of the same pitch or name is called an octave. In addition, each part of the musical scale containing the seven basic steps is also called an octave. The entire sound range is divided into several octaves. In musical practice, the starting note of each octave is considered to be the sound of C.

The entire tone range studied in the course of elementary theory of music consists of seven complete octaves and four tones that form two incomplete octaves located at the two ends of the piano keyboard. Octaves are named from bottom to top as follows: sub-contra octave, counter octave, major octave, minor octave, first octave, second octave, third octave, fourth octave, fifth octave.

A certain interaction of the absolute pitch of sounds in a musical structure is called a musical pitch. The history of musical words is inextricably linked with the history of tuning forks. It was the sound of the first octave of the lya that was accepted as the basic sound of many tuning forks. This standard sound source, the tuning fork, was invented by the English musician *J.Shore* in 1711, and it was 419.9 Hz. Later, it changed several times, and finally received the status of a musical note at the international conference held in Vienna in 1885, and it is still valid today.

Since that time, the sound of music has been based on the first octave of the lya sound vibrating 440 times a second. Each octave of the musical structure is divided into 12 equal parts - semitones. This type of musical notation is called tempered notation. It differs from the natural sound line (*soz*) in that all semitones in the octave are equal.

Since each octave is divided into 12 equal semitones, a semitone is the smallest interval between sounds in a musical structure. An interval formed by two semitones is called a whole tone. The loudspeaker has two semitones and five

whole tones. Whole tones formed between the main steps are divided into semitones. The sounds heard when pressing the black keys of the piano are divided into semitones. Thus, each octave consists of 12 equally spaced sounds. Depending on the musical practice, it is possible to raise or lower each main step of the sound line. In this case, the raised or lowered steps are called derivative steps. Therefore, the name of the derivative steps comes from the name of the main steps.

The total volume of a musical sound range from the lowest sound to the highest sound is called the musical range. The range of the human voice or the sound of an instrument refers to the general musical range that they can represent (for example, the piano range A2 - s5). The representation of sounds in the letter structure, in addition to writing sounds with syllables, the method of writing with letters based on the Latin alphabet is also widely used.

The seven main steps are defined as follows:

C	D	E	F	G	A	H
Do	Re	Mi	Fa	Sol	Lya	Si

The letter structure of note sounds is based on the Latin alphabet. The reason for the somewhat incorrect arrangement of sounds in alphabetical order is that in the Middle Ages, the main sound was considered to be lya (**a**), followed by the sound of si bemol (**b**). Musical sounds are written using notes. They consist of empty or painted circles.

Since the sounds have different lengths, they are marked with vertical sticks (styles), flags, and ribs - additional horizontal lines to combine short-length sounds into one group. To accurately determine the pitch of sounds, notes are placed on a musical path consisting of five parallel lines. Lines are numbered from bottom to top. At the beginning of the note path, a vertical line connecting five lines is placed. This vertical line is called the starting line.

It should be noted that teaching music theory and literacy to students is commendable. I believe that it is our duty and mission to deliver such cultural heritage to the next generation with care and proper execution.

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